

An Imaginative Proposal for a Sustainable Four State Solution

Some states (Lebanon, Syria) and territories (Palestinian) have proven incapable of being peaceable neighbors to Israel by allowing the festering of anti-semitic, fundamentalist religious movements driven by Iran.

Other states (Egypt, Jordan) have proven capable of being peaceful neighbors to Israel, because they are committed to religious moderation, international citizenship, and harmonious relationships with Saudi Arabia.

Israel is itself on an unsustainable, dual track, demographically shifting rapidly from a Jewish-majority to a Jewish-minority state, while succumbing politically and militarily to a religious fundamentalism which seeks to take ever more lands to restore a lost ancestral ideal.

Given all this, neither a single-state solution (which is tantamount to no Jewish state at all) nor a two-state solution (which is tantamount to the political enfranchisement of anti-semitism) is viable.

The only viable path may be something no one has yet considered: a four state solution.

1. Jordan, already the guardians of peace at Al-Aqsa, annexes as a new state with a Palestinian- and Muslim-majority citizenship, a large swath of land contiguous with its current western border, encompassing much of the West Bank, with an ultimate westward border in east Jerusalem.
2. Egypt, already committed to intelligence-sharing with Israel for the sake of its security, annexes as a new state with a Palestinian- and Muslim-majority citizenship the southern half of the current territory of Gaza.
3. Displaced Christians (Palestinian, Assyrian, Armenian, Coptic, Russian, Ukrainian, Eastern Rite Catholic, et al) form a new, non-contiguous state as a league of buffer zones between Muslim-majority and Jewish-majority populations. The United Nations would charter this state, provide it with its initial funding and administrative framework, as well as an international peacekeeping military force. Though non-contiguous, this state would be centered in places of special religious importance to Christians (e.g., Nazareth, Capernaum, Bethlehem), yet also encompass sufficient land to be of strategic security value to preserve harmonious Jewish-Muslim relations.
4. Israel compromises and coordinates with the three aforementioned states on a redrawing of its own borders and voluntary interstate migration plan to maintain its security and its long-term viability as a Jewish-majority yet democratic state.

While Palestinians who have dreamt of a state would not find their dream fulfilled, they would have what they seek most, an end to displacement and the possibility of a lasting, sustainable peace. A formal agreement between Egypt and Jordan would provide for the reunion of families and free travel between these annexed Palestinian states.